

Animal Welfare Research

Network (AWRN) EDI Audit

EDI Questions

1. How long have you been a member of AWRN?
 - Less than 12 months
 - 1-3 years
 - 4+ years
 - Prefer not to say

2. Where are you primarily based?
 - England
 - Northern Ireland
 - Republic of Ireland
 - Scotland
 - Wales
 - International
 - If international, please provide details [free text]
 - Prefer to Self Describe [free text]

3. What type of institution do you currently work for or study at?
 - Industry
 - Charity Sector
 - Policy / Government
 - Academic Institution
 - Other Research Institution
 - Prefer to Self Describe [free text]

4. Which of these best describes the level of your position at the organisation?
Where more than one applies, please consider your main role.
 - Senior (e.g. senior management position, professor or company owner)
 - Mid-level (e.g. senior lecturer, senior research fellow, farm manager or section lead)
 - Intermediate (e.g. lecturer, research fellow, researcher or senior technician)
 - Entry-Level (e.g. research assistant, teaching associate, technician, farm hand, researcher)

- Student (e.g. Masters or PhD student)
- Prefer to Self Describe (please give details, if you wish) [free text]

5. What is your current working pattern?

- Full Time
- Part Time
- Flexible / Ad-hoc
- Prefer not to say
- Prefer to Self Describe (please give details, if you wish) [free text]

6. What is your age?

- Under 18
- 18-24
- 25-34
- 35-44
- 45-54
- 55-64
- 65+
- Prefer not to say

7. What gender do you identify as?

- Man
- Non-Binary / Genderqueer
- Woman
- Prefer not to say
- Prefer to Self-Describe [free text]

8. Do you consider yourself to be transgender?

- Yes
- No
- Prefer not to say

9. How would you describe your sexual orientation?

- Asexual
- Bi/Bisexual
- Gay Man
- Gay Woman / Lesbian
- Heterosexual / Straight
- Other sexual orientation
- Prefer not to say

- Prefer to Self-Describe [free text]

10. How would you describe your ethnicity?

Please choose one option that best describes your ethnic group or background

Asian or Asian British

- Bangladeshi
- Chinese
- Indian
- Pakistani
- Any other Asian background

Black, African, Caribbean or Black British

- African
- Caribbean
- Any other Black, African or Caribbean background

Mixed or Multiple ethnic groups

- White and Black Caribbean
- White and Black African
- White and Asian
- Any other Mixed or Multiple ethnic background

White or White British

- English, Welsh, Scottish, Northern Irish or British
- Irish
- Gypsy or Irish Traveller
- Any other White background

Other ethnic group

- Arab
- Any other ethnic group

Prefer not to say

Prefer to self describe [Free Text]

11. How would you classify your religious beliefs/affiliation?

- Non-religious, Atheist or Agnostic

- Christian (Including Catholic, Protestant, Orthodox, and all other Christian denominations)
- Buddhist
- Hindu
- Humanist
- Jewish
- Muslim
- Sikh
- Spiritual
- Any other religion (prefer to self describe) [Free Text]
- Prefer not to say

Please note, responding to this survey, and these two questions in particular will not be considered a formal disclosure of any disability, long-term health condition, or neurodiversity to AWRN.

12. Do you consider yourself to have any disability or long-term health condition?

- A condition affecting motor, cognitive, social and emotional skills, speech, communication or language.
- Hearing impairment or deafness
- Long-term illness (for example, cancer, HIV, diabetes, chronic heart disease or epilepsy)
- Mental health condition (for example, depression, anxiety disorder, schizophrenia)
- Physical disability or mobility issue (for example, impaired use of limbs, or use of a wheelchair or mobility aid)
- Visual impairment not corrected by glasses or blindness
- Another disability, health condition, or impairment affecting daily life
- No
- Prefer not to say

13. Do you consider yourself to have a neurodiverse condition (diagnosed or undiagnosed)?

Tick all that apply

- Yes - Autism
- Yes - ADHD
- Yes - Dyslexia
- Yes - Dyspraxia
- Yes - Other - Self describe: [free text]
- No

- I don't know
- Prefer not to say

14. Are you a parent/guardian or caregiver of one or more dependents (e.g. children under 18, or ageing parents)? [Tick all that apply]

- Yes – Parent
- Yes – Parent of child(ren) with special needs
- Yes – Carer for one or more adult(s)
- No
- Prefer not to say
- Prefer to Self Describe (please give details, if you wish) [Free Text]

15. What best describes your relationship status?

- Co-habiting or living with a partner
- Married or in a civil partnership
- Separated, divorced or civil partnership dissolved
- Single
- Widowed or a surviving partner from a civil partnership
- Long-term relationship (not cohabiting or living with a partner)
- Other (specify, if you wish) [Free Text]
- Prefer not to say

Educational Background

This section includes some questions in relation to your education and that of your parents, to consider social mobility across generations.

1. What is the highest level of education you have completed?

If you are currently studying, please select the highest level obtained.

- Doctorate
- Postgraduate / Masters
- Professional Qualification
- Undergraduate Degree / Diploma
- Primary / Elementary
- Secondary / High School
- Other – Self describe [free text]
- Prefer not to say

2. What best describes the majority of your secondary school education?

- Received secondary education outside of the UK
 - Home schooling
 - A UK state-run or state-funded school
 - Independent or fee-paying school
 - Independent or fee-paying school, where I received a bursary covering 90% or more of my tuition
 - Unknown
 - Other – Self describe [free text]
 - Prefer not to say
3. What is the highest level of education your parent(s) / guardian(s) have completed?

Where there may be a disparity - please select the highest achieved qualification.

- Doctorate
 - Postgraduate / Masters
 - Primary / Elementary
 - Professional Qualification
 - Secondary / High School
 - Undergraduate Degree / Diploma
 - Unknown
 - Other – Self describe [free text]
 - Prefer not to say
4. What was the occupation of your main household earner when you were aged about 14?
- Managerial (e.g., manager, supervisor, executive)
 - Professional (e.g., doctor, lawyer, engineer, teacher)
 - Semi-routine and routine (e.g., labourer, cleaner)
 - Semi-skilled (e.g., factory worker, sales assistant, driver)
 - Skilled (e.g., electrician, plumber, technician, craftsman)

If you finished school after 1980, were you eligible for free school meals at any point during your school years?

- Yes
- No
- Not applicable
- I do not know / unsure
- Prefer not to say

Your experience with the AWRN

Next, there are some questions regarding your experience with the AWRN and your perceptions of EDI in relation to the AWRN

1. I feel like I belong within AWRN:
 - Strongly Agree
 - Agree
 - Neither agree, nor disagree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly Disagree

2. AWRN actively promotes fair treatment of all members regardless of their different diversity characteristics:
 - Strongly Agree
 - Agree
 - Neither agree, nor disagree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly Disagree

3. AWRN provides me with the support (including training, safe spaces, mentoring etc.) I need to engage with people from all backgrounds and experiences:
 - Strongly Agree
 - Agree
 - Neither agree, nor disagree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly Disagree

4. I feel comfortable talking about equality, diversity and inclusion within AWRN:
 - Strongly Agree
 - Agree
 - Neither agree, nor disagree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly Disagree

5. I feel empowered to make positive contributions to AWRN:
 - Strongly Agree
 - Agree
 - Neither agree, nor disagree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly Disagree

6. Does AWRN have a clear Equality, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI) strategy or vision?

- Yes
- No
- Not that I am aware of
- Unsure

7. I am confident that AWRN would deal with any concerns about harassment, victimisation, or discrimination appropriately:

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Neither agree, nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

8. I have personally experienced harassment, victimisation, or discrimination within AWRN:

Please note, as the survey is anonymous, responding to this question is not considered a formal disclosure to AWRN of a concern. We would however encourage anyone with any concerns to contact the AWRN to discuss their concerns further. This should be m.a.palmer@qub.ac.uk and awrn-manager@bristol.ac.uk

- Yes
- No
- Unsure
- Prefer not to say
- Other (self describe) [Free Text]

9. If you have personally experienced harassment, victimisation or discrimination, please state which protected characteristic(s), if any, this related to [please tick one or more boxes]

- age
- disability
- gender reassignment
- marriage / civil partnership
- pregnancy / maternity
- race
- religion or belief
- sex
- sexual orientation

10. I have witnessed harassment, victimisation, or discrimination within AWRN:

- Yes
- No
- Unsure
- Prefer not to say
- Other (self describe) [Free Text]

11. If Yes, please state which protected characteristic(s), if any, this related to:

Please tick one or more boxes:

- age
- disability
- gender reassignment
- marriage / civil partnership
- pregnancy / maternity
- race
- religion or belief
- sex
- sexual orientation

Free text questions

We would appreciate you answering the following free text questions as they will allow us to draw a greater insight into your experiences. These questions can be answered in bullet point form if easier or these spaces can be left blank if you prefer not to say.

1. Are there any barriers or difficulties you have experienced related to equality, diversity or inclusivity when engaging with animal welfare research in general?
 - Free text
2. Thinking about all the AWRN's activities (including in-person and online meetings, communications and funding schemes) in terms of equality, diversity and inclusion, what does AWRN currently do well?
 - Free text
3. Thinking about those same activities in terms of equality, diversity and inclusion, what could the AWRN do better? Please feel free to cite good practice you have witnessed/experienced at other organisations.
 - Free text
4. What equality, diversity and AWRN initiatives / activities should the AWRN focus on during the next 12 months?
 - Free text

5. Do you have any other comments about any equality, diversity and inclusion aspects you have not yet been asked about or would like to share more detail about?

- Free text